

LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF PAREMIA REPRESENTING INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS AND THEIR USAGE IN THE PROCESS OF THE LANGUAGE LEARNING

Daminova Charos Zaydilla qizi

Chirchiq Oliy Tank Qo‘mondonlik Muhandislik bilim yurti

Tillar kafedrası ingliz tili o‘qituvchisi

ABSTRACT

In this article describes the similarities and differences between paremias in the different languages, proverbs that express the culture and mentality of nations, and express interpersonal relationships. Furthermore the article explains the ways of increasing the speaking skill by using paremias in the speech.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada turli tillardagi paremiyalar, xalqlar madaniyati va mentalitetini ifodalovchi, shaxslararo munosabatlarni ifodalovchi maqollar o‘rtasidagi o‘xshashlik va farqlar bayon etilgan. Bundan tashqari maqolada nutqda paremiyalarni qo‘llash orqali nutq mahoratini oshirish yo‘llari tushuntiriladi.

Introduction

Today, intensive research is being conducted on proverbs, and the study of all aspects of proverbs is one of the main tasks of the field of paremiology. When studying the comparative aspects of paremias expressing interpersonal relations, we cannot help but touch on their linguistic and cultural aspects.

Literature Review

Proverbs and sayings are the main elements of the language worldview. People can understand themselves only thanks to the language in which historical, social and moral experience has been accumulated. Proverbs and proverbs have a unique quality - they reflect in any way the characteristics of the entire nation, such as everyday life, preferences, attitude to various spheres of life, philosophical, religious, moral and aesthetic views. A proverb is a short well-known saying that expresses a widely held truth or belief. Many linguists A. Afanasiev, M. Dubrovin, A. Potebnya and others devoted their works to proverbs and proverbs. In the 20th century, another direction of their study - the linguo-cultural direction - appeared. They began to be studied as stereotypes that describe our lives. Proverbs and sayings become an integral part of our

mentality, which forms the basis of the vocabulary word image of each nation. However, there are still difficulties in distinguishing between these two concepts. In general, the article is well-known and reproducible. Paremiyas are said to express truth based on common sense or experience. In fact, a word can be defined as a written or spoken linguistic expression that is remembered because of its content or structure. Usually there is something more meaningful and understandable than what is said in a proverb.

Moreover, today we can find different definitions of proverbs and sayings. Thus, Longman's Dictionary of Modern English defines a proverb as: a short well-known statement containing advice about life in general.¹ M. Dubrovin emphasizes the conceptual side of the term. He writes that a proverb is a short sentence that people often say. According to him, this is a true statement that reflects the ancient history of a particular people, something that informs or tells the receivers about human life and problems in general. Paremiyas are proverbs found in many cultures and often very old. We need paremiyas in communication because they reflect who we are. Paremiyas are very widely used in interpersonal relationships.²

Research methodology

Soviet and Russian social psychologist and sociologist G.M. Andreeva, interpersonal relations are an integral part of all social consciousness. In this regard, G. M. Andreeva says: "The nature of interpersonal relations, if they are not equated with social relations, but if they see in them a specific type of relations arising from each type of social relations and beyond them, then can be understood".³ It can be explained as follows: If a person loses his job to a friend, you: "What you lose on the swings, you make up for on the roundabouts" "closed" you can say. If a child comes to a difficult task and cannot find a way, you can say: "**It's good fishing in troubled waters**", i.e. "**Loy ichidan dur ajrat**". All this points to the fact that paremiyas have a role in the precise expression of our relationships.

According to psychology, a person is a social being. During his life, he communicates directly with other people and thereby realizes his social essence. Such communication takes place in different groups. As long as a person lives in society, he is always in communication and interaction with different people, and these communication processes always take place in a group of people. That is why interpersonal relations are one of the most important problems.

¹ Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English. <http://www.ldoceonline.com/dictionary/pdf>

² Дубровин М. Английские и русские пословицы. Москва, 1993. -С 16.

³ Андреева Г.М. Социальная психология. — М., 1998. -С. 1-5.

Analysis and result

Here, we will give examples of favorite family sayings and paremies that remind the mutual love of family members. For example:

English: If we translate the proverb **“To lead a cat and dog life”** into Uzbek, it means ***mushuk va itdek urushadi***.

This is expressed in the Uzbek language by the proverb: **“Er-xotin urushi, doka ro‘mol qurishi”** It reflects the relationship between family or husband and wife and is often used to add warmth to the relationship.

The word **“Cat and Dog”** in English Paremia gives its meaning **“it va mushuk”** in Uzbek. But here these words come in a figurative sense with the meaning of **“husband and wife”**. Although this sentence is a common simile in the culture of that nation, it seems like a rather silly simile to the Uzbek nation. For this reason, this proverb cannot be used with a direct translation, and it is appropriate to use its alternative in a manner specific to the national culture.

It is known that every nation has its own customs and traditions, and every person in the society practices and believes in them. We saw the difference in the way of life of the two peoples, although not much in the family matter. We will show it as another example. For example:

English: **“Go down the ladder when thou marriest a wife;
Go up when thou chooseth a friend.”**

If we look at the Uzbek equivalent:

“Xotining bilan birlashganda zinadan pastga tushasan;

Do‘st tanlanganda yuqoriga ko‘tarilasan”. It is the word **“ladder”** used in the English version that means high rank. The meaning is that the woman is recommending to choose a friend rather than your rank. This poem, which reflects friendship and family relations, is presented in Uzbek in a slightly different way. That is:

**“Xotin so‘zini qondirar,
Er urug‘idan tondirar.”**

It can be seen that phrases such as **“er urug‘i”** or **“ayol urug‘i”** are words specific to the Uzbek nation. In fact, the word **“family”** in its full and broad sense includes father, mother and child in the scientific sense. Marriage is the basis of the relationship between husband and wife, and blood kinship is the basis of the relationship between parents and children. In the rules of Islam and state legal norms, a lot of attention is paid to the issues of marriage and consanguinity. That is why it is not for nothing that such bonds and relationships are considered very sacred for the Muslim people.

Conclusion

In fact, it is one of the important stages of our work to examine the linguistic and cultural characteristics of English and Uzbek proverbs expressing interpersonal relations, which is one of the main parts of our research work, and to study their similarities and differences. For this reason, based on the theories of the scientists mentioned above, we will try to prove our points by deeply analyzing some paremias in Uzbek and English languages. With the help of examples, we will try to show to what extent the people's lifestyle is expressed in them and show the similarities and differences between the proverbs that exist in two languages and reflect the attitude of individuals.

List of used literature

1. Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English.
<http://www.ldoceonline.com/dictionary/pdf>
2. Дубровин М. Английские и русские пословицы. Москва, 1993. -С 16.
3. Андреева Г.М. Социальная психология. — М., 1998. -С. 1-5.